

Prevalence Of Students With Learning Difficulties In Basic Arithmetic Operations In The Subject Of Mathematics At Elementary Level

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 29, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning, Mathematics, Schools, Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5110685</p>	<p><i>Purpose of the study: This research paper was conducted to determine the prevalence of the students with learning difficulties in arithmetic operation mathematical skills at elementary, specifically for the students studying in 5th grade in mainstream schools. Almost 11.4% of the screen out students of all mainstream schools are recognized as having a learning difficulty in arithmetic operation mathematical techniques, bifurcating 10.5% male and 16.5% female students. Researches supported the notion that the prevalence of students with learning difficulties in mathematics increased dramatically in the past 20 years, both in male and female students. Whereas the majority of male and female students significantly differ in the arithmetic operation mathematical skills remarkably. Different researchers mention that the main reasons for these learning difficulties are the teacher's pedagogical skills, missing teaching methods for mathematics, the delivery style of the teacher, and the students' learning styles. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that the teachers' training should improve teachers' instructional techniques to overcome the learning difficulties from the mainstream part to uplift the academic strength in this modern, scientific and dynamic era.</i></p>

Introduction

For students with normal IQ levels (90-120), the term 'learning disabilities' is employed. Because of disturbances to some psychological processes, notably language, the causes for their deficiencies are regarded as internal. In this study, however, the phrases learning problems are employed to address this issue.

However, the word learning difficulties does not suggest that students have intelligence levels but might suffer physical, educational, emotional, and environment-related challenges. Therefore, the researcher chooses the term learning trouble rather than learning impairment, given the educational solutions for both groups are the same (having learning disabilities and learning difficulties).

Mathematical learning problems are a significant concern. Mathematical learning issues produce obstacles and hurdles in public school learning in conventional classes. In addition, various studies have indicated that many children have difficulty acquiring math (Dowker, 2004, 2005; Geary, 1993).

The study has revealed many factors that are causing problems such as insufficient pedagogical expertise for teachers, a strict educational style, a lack of professional involvement for teachers, wrong choice and use of inappropriate teaching styles, random selection, and service of interactive, audiovisual aids, lack of training/refresher courses for teachers, inadequate and non-relevant assessment of mathematics teaching.

Mathematics is a mandatory subject for 1 to 10 years in Pakistan's national curriculum. However, Maths learning is not an easy chore for most students in private and public institutions around the country. Mathematics curricula offer a highly distinctive type of information that demands a particular attitude, a mindset, and a conflict amongst students (Ellis, 2011; Govt of Pakistan, 2006; Rojan, 2008).

Regrettably, educators teaching at many private and public institutions do not grow and flourish the essential skills essential for studying mathematics in children. Consequently, students cannot link to mathematics, even after being promoted to secondary classes (secondary courses) (Government of Pakistan, 2009).

An organized and comprehensive study on primary learning mathematics is limited in Pakistan, notably in Punjab. The survey carried out in mathematics showed no accurate and true image of mathematics teaching and learning in secondary education. Some studies carried out at the primary level focus solely on mathematics education, but no study emphasizes the pupils' learning difficulties in mathematics.

In Pakistan, elementary education in mathematics suffers from teaching skills and student's absorption of mathematical ideas. Teachers often cannot adequately express mathematical concepts, adding to students who are unable to understand mathematics. This research study aimed to find out the frequency of students struggling to learn mathematics in Punjab particularly.

The study was carried out to achieve the following aims; 1) Identification of the prevalence in the mathematical arithmetic operation of students with learning difficulties, 2) comparison of mathematical learning challenges between students' males and females, and 3) to evaluate the learning problems of rural/urban students in mathematics. The following questions have been answered in this study; 1) what is the predominance in the field of mathematical arithmetical operation for students with learning difficulties? 2) what is the difference between male and female students while learning difficulties in mathematics? And 3) what is the difference between rural and urban students in the difficulty of learning mathematics?

Mathematical learning issues are one of the main concerns for primary and high school students in Punjab. Mathematical learning issues cannot be recognized and treated correctly following their unique areas of mathematics. Learning difficulties in the theme of mathematics is one of the fundamental causes for low mathematical accomplishment. Students with learning mathematics issues may not do well in their jobs. The teachers often fail to understand the nature of the challenges facing the students during their careers.

Public school teachers did not know how to diagnose children with learning the topic of mathematics with difficulty. This is the first research that helps math teachers identify pupils with learning challenges, especially at the elementary level in mathematics. This research is also the first to allow students with difficulty in mathematical knowledge to know the degree of prevalence.

Knowledge of the prevalence of students with learning problems in mathematics can improve the quality of learning for instructors. Thus, this study is successful in the corrective teaching of students with learning challenges in mathematics and in improving educational attainment.

Literature Review

Mathematics is a metaphorical language that enables people to think about the record and communicate thoughts concerning connection and quantity elements (Lerner and Johns, 2015, p. 478). Mathematics is a field of numbers and space, according to Sidhu (2000). Knowledge of magnitude, amount, and measurement in mathematics. The skill of logical thinking is also mentioned in mathematics.

The mathematical child finds a range of different cultural instruments in several civilizations (Butterworth, 2005). These tools include material skills like knowledge and arithmetical terminology, forms recognition, counting, and subsidization. The tools also include abstract algebraic operations, data analysis, measuring, and geometry (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, NCTM, 2000). The relevance of these tools for constructing the basic notions of mathematics cannot be overlooked.

All individuals can "react without language or abstract thinking, or much chance to operate its universe, to the numerical features of their visual reality" (Butterworth, 2005a, p. 5). Butterworth (2005) describes these tasks as numerical problems that need such answers. He says the numbers of a child are innate. Several studies illustrate how toddlers aged between a few weeks and 13 months appear to be numerical (Cooper and Starkey, 1980; Antell & Keating, 1983; Starkey, 1990; Brannon, 2002).

Some study investigations have shown that even when children are just two, they know rudimentary number perceptions, and they can subitize the numbers with up to four or five things (Strauss and Curtis, 1981). As a result, the Number may be described as "an invariant feature of a range of objects describing their numerical measurement" (Smitsman and Van Loosbroek, 1990).

Numerosity for numeracy and mathematics is the base and ladder. These two concepts were discussed by many authors using distinct approaches. For example, Sousa (2008) characterizes mathematics as "the capacity of measurement, counting and simplistic addition and subtraction without direct instruction for determining the number of things in a small collection" (p. 1). This idea is similar to Dowker's idea of numeracy (2004). Its 10 components are (i) counting of things, (ii) orally counting, (iii) writing and reading, (iv) units, tens and centuries of common numbers, (v) word questions, (vi) evidencing, (vii) translating, (ix) estimating and (x) re-sourcing.

It is assumed that numbers, which are instinctual, serve as a scale ladder that allows mathematics to develop. Thus, the term numerosity refers to the primary ability for quantity recognition, and numeracy denotes one or more of Dowker's ten numeracy components (2004). However, the word mathematics alludes to a broader significance of digitality, including data management, geometry, and the other domains indicated in the NCTM (in Chinn, 2004).

Dowker (2004) considers that mathematics is not easy since data management, measurement, geometry, and many various jobs are concerned. The Department of Education and Skills also provided the same concept (DFES, 1999). In Chinn (2004), the key 12 mathematical elements established by the National Teachers' Council for Mathematics (NCTM), USA, are presented. These are: explaining mathematical concepts, problem-solving, and mathematical reasoning, using mathematics in real life, sensitivity to the logic of outcomes, estimating, sufficient computational skill, algebraic intelligence, measurement, geometry, statistics, and probability. This would most probably not have allowed the children to understand numeracy components at an early level, which sometimes had problems with numeracy and subsequently with mathematics (Dowker, 2004).

Chinn (2004) stresses that "there are various explanations why people in mathematics can achieve little" (p. 3). But a disparity in all or some of the skills, concepts, and areas proposed by NCTM, USA may be one explanation. "Not widely identified or well understood are certain learning challenges in numeracy" (Butterworth, 2005a). In this domain, however, several types of research focused on challenging areas for pupils to calculate. Some children may have difficulty in all main regions of arithmetic (Landerl, 2004), but only some specific mathematical zones are in disarray (Temple, 1991). We should not thus classify the students as good or terrible but instead solve the challenges they are facing in particular areas of mathematics (Dowker, 2004). It is also quite important, after recognizing them correctly, to solve the challenges that face them.

Content and Scope of Mathematics

The curriculum for mathematics has undergone substantial revisions in several states (Australian Education Council, 1990; National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM), 2000; Romberg, 1995). Nowadays based on socio-constructive learning theory was the most commonly promoted teaching technique. Students are supposed to participate actively and critically in their learning practices. This means less guidance for teachers, an additional inductive method, and extra group work and exploration. Modern approaches need to be less practical and less memorial, which leads to more research, problem-solving, discovery, reflection, and discussion. The lesson of instructor guidance is not enough. The study of school mathematics should be as evocative as the familiar early infant experience for children (Mastrioperi & Scruggs, 2002).

Early Learning in Mathematics

The learning of numbers begins at an early age with parents and others in various natural methods (Aubrey, 2001). Preschool kids seem to comprehend ordinality, counts, numeracy, and rudimentary arithmetic, even deprived of direct teaching (Ginsberg, 1997). This casual numeric understanding provides the solid basis for learning forthcoming abilities and conceptual growth at the start of school. When children get to school, they find a much more formalized version of mathematics for the first time.

Definition of Learning Difficulties

U.S. Department of Education (2012) categorized learning difficulties as described by Lerner and John; The term "specific learning disability" means a disorder in one or more of the basic psychological processes involved in understanding or using language, spoken or written, which disorder may manifest itself in imperfect ability to listen, think, speak, spell, or to do mathematical calculations. Such terms include perceptual disabilities, brain injury, minimal brain dysfunction, dyslexia, and developmental aphasia. Such term does not include a learning problem that is primarily the result of visual, hearing or motor disabilities; of mental retardation; of emotional disturbance or environmental, cultural, or economic disadvantage".

Above US education department definition of learning disabilities contain three elements; 1) in one or more psychological processes, the individual has a learning problem that refers to mental capacity, memory, audiological perception, visual perception, spoken language, and reasoning. 2) persons with learning difficulties faced with speech, reading/listening difficulties, writing (word recognition, understanding) and mathematics, and the difficulty of learning faced by persons without causes like visual or hearing loss, motor impairments, intellectual disabilities, emotional disturbances, socio-economic factors and cultural disorder (Lerner & John, ss 2015).

There is so much criticism on the U. S . Education department definition of learning disabilities, and there is no practical use of the USA definition. The other definition of US NJCLD seems to more appropriate to clarify this syndrome. NJCLD is as under;

"Learning disability is a general term that refers to a heterogeneous group of disorders manifested by significant difficulties in the acquisition and use of listening, speaking, reading, writing, reasoning, or mathematical abilities. These disorders are intrinsic to the individual and presumed to be due to central nervous system dysfunction. Thus, even though a learning disorder may occur concomitantly with other handicapping conditions (e.g., sensory impairment, mental retardation, social and emotional disturbance) or environmental influences (e.g., cultural differences, insufficient/ inappropriate instruction, psychogenic factors), it is not the direct result of those conditions or influences" (Hammill, Leigh, McNutt, and Larsen, 1987, P.109).

Diagnosis of Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

Two strategies to detect children with learning difficulty were revealed by Lerner & Johns (2015): 1) reaction to intervention with suspected problems; or 2) extensive assessment of students with suspected learning issues. The most valid and significant diagnostic instruments for diagnosing children with learning impairments who require aid in learning mathematics are diagnosed in the many fields of mathematics. The research also highlights the necessity for learners with learning problems to be taught in mathematics to understand the issue areas.

Causes of Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

Several causes for the low performance in mathematics have been identified. Many individuals would probably interpret these explanations as general occurrences, as mentioned by Denvir (2006). However, the

contributing elements might be a disruption or issues that occur during the time of childbirth in the neurological system.

Inappropriate teaching: The poor quality of teaching and teaching that fails to meet their unique requirements and differences are key determinants of learners with learning difficulties in mathematics (Ginsberg, 1997; Reusser, 2000). It is more necessary to analyze the quality and kind of instruction the children receive before analyzing the causes of learning difficulties inside a learner. Some of these causes can be combined as a basis for their issues. For example, a barrier in particular regions might have confronted the others who should have the usual intellectual capacities. Chinn and Ashcroft (2007) highlighted the concerns of kids with learning difficulties.

Frequent reviews and revisions: Many of these shortcomings recur in a similar classroom, unfortunately, and so have a growing consequence upon the children's difficulty. Much more has to be done to enhance education quality to lower the frequency of mathematical learning challenges. Unfortunately, however, teachers, academics, and psychologists have traditionally been concerned far more in pupil variables than in instruction since they have failed to study mathematics (Fleischner, 1994; Troutman & Lichtenberg, 2003).

Inadequate curriculum: The arithmetic word problems are a major challenge to the curriculum in prime grades. These problems are taught to elementary school children to know how to use the methods and tactics of mathematics in their daily lives. However, for many years, numerous researches have discussed that broad practice with common arithmetic word problems leads learners to approach word problems monotonously, artificially, and regularly to understand the specific arithmetical technique needed to obtain the correct results (Mulligan, 1997).

Assessment and students with Learning Difficulties

The prevailing impacts of the evaluations on pupils' behavior. The problem here is for every evaluation to be planned and designed away from educational institutions and thus lose links with the actual condition of the learning setting. It is also usual for evaluations to be carried out to analyze issues that are not too easy to examine, which typically allow procedures or information to be recalled more than required. Nevertheless, the recent study by Hindal (2007) shows the overwhelming impact of the evaluation on a call-back measurement activity in almost all cases.

The goals underlying mathematics education must comprise developing concepts and comprehending the use of mathematical knowledge in unexpected contexts. This methodology is not simple to master, but in new practical settings, the teachings can be quite valuable if the benefits for such evaluation tasks are healthy. Unfortunately, it is difficult for such problems to be addressed initially, and research to discover the methods used for conceptual understanding and use should then be carried out.

The scholars have tried to examine the challenges of mathematics by several times. Many research papers have identified challenges to the methods for learners to study mathematics. We want to identify the key study of learning obstacles in mathematics while focusing on elementary school children.

It may be hard because numerous factors, such as delay in development, lack of expertise, language challenges, motor, and perceptual impairments, loss of memory, frequent school absences, and mathematical anxieties, can lead to poor learning or issues of the mathematical basics.

Prevalence of Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

There have been reports that six percent (06%) of school children have serious problems learning mathematical concepts and competencies (Fleischner&Manheimer, 1997). Still, a much higher proportion of students had low mathematical results, showed negative results, and showed no confidence in the subject's ability to improve. As a result, some children (and adults) have acquired learning hardship when mathematics skills should be used (Battista, 1999).

Early experiences of failure, whether via lack of appropriate familiar learning in the preschool years, or lack of explicit teaching in school, can swiftly weaken the formation of the strong foundation of concepts and abilities needed for continued progress. Butterworth (1999, p.298) has observed: "There are many reasons for being bad at any school subject. However, school Maths is like a house of cards: the cards in the bottom layer must be firmly and accurately constructed to support the next layer up. Each stage depends on the last".

Pervasiveness analyses show that the majority of the mainstream public schools comprise students with learning challenges. These computations are typical in Australia because some students cannot recognize that the official evaluation is not mandatory. However, a national Australian special education survey (Berry Andrews, Elkins, & Burge, 1979) suggested stages of eleven percent (11%) with an extreme of thirty percent (30%) in approximately all the grades of governmental, educational institutions. A report issued by the OECD in 1999 showed incidence for pupils with mathematical knowledge deficiency between 12 and 16 percent. This finding has been confirmed by the modern Australian National Mathematical Student Survey (ANMS) (Brady, Milton, & Rohl, 2000). A figure of independent Australian and International studies also documented the pupils as the larger cluster with particular academic necessities provide additional support for increasing numbers (Westwood, 2000; Wallace, Anderson, & Bartholomay, 2003; McKinnon, Gordon, & Prunty, 2000).

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study has been descriptive. The study research design was employed to detect the incidence of Learning difficulties (LDs) students in mathematics in mainstream public schools of the Punjab province.

Population and Sampling

The population for this study was all 5th-grade elementary school students in the province of Punjab. The research sample was picked randomly from the population. Because of the geographical limitations set by Punjab, Lahore's Directorate of Staff Development, for the professional development of primary educators in this province all Lahore district schools were grouped into 40 clusters. Two schools from each cluster were picked randomly. Sample distribution is provided as following, gender and area wise. In each school, the identification of LD students in Mathematics included all instructors who taught mathematics in the 5th grade. The sample sizes were 2392 elementary school children in the district of Lahore.

Numbers of Students = Numbers of Clusters x 2

Numbers of Schools = 40 x 2 = 80

Numbers of Children in Grade-5 in Govt. Schools = 19999

Instrumentation

Two stages of data gathering were completed. In the first part of the checklist, observations on students' academic performance and conduct in mathematics in the class were taken up by instructors. The criterion for the students to be included in the second stage has been devised. The second phase was delivered to children through the Student Diagnostic Test (SDT). The investigator himself managed the checklist and performance test at all levels.

Data Collection and Analysis

Characteristics of Sample

Table of Demographic information (age and gender of student, area of the school) is given below;

Table 1

Frequency Distribution (Gender & Living Area)		
Category	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percent (%)
Male	1150	48.08
Female	1242	51.92
Rural	1230	51.42
Urban	1162	48.58

Table 2 Low and high achievement comparison in Arithmetic operation Diagnostic Test

Achievement Category	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Low Achiever	260	0.46	2389	-11.631	0.001
High Achiever	2132	7.49	2359		

**P* < .05 Significance Level

Table 2 confirms that low achievers students got significantly (**P* .001 < .05, Significance Level) fewer marks as compared to the high achievers' students in the diagnostic test for arithmetic operations in the learning of mathematical skills (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division).

Table 3

Frequency distribution of Teachers Score of Screening Checklist Learning Difficulties in Mathematics

Range of Score	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
30-33	1560	50
34-37	676	22
38-41	373	12
42-45	265	8
46-48	246	8
Total	3120	100

***P* < .05 Significance Level

Table 4

Frequency Distribution of Item Wise Scores of Arithmetic Operations Diagnostic Test (AODT)

Sr. #	Item No.	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
1	A.1	910	(38.0)	1412	(59.0)	70	(2.9)	2392	(100)
2	A.2	702	(29.3)	1620	(67.7)	70	(2.9)	2392	(100)
3	A.3	430	(18.0)	1899	(79.4)	63	(2.6)	2392	(100)
4	A.4	713	(29.8)	1468	(61.4)	211	(8.8)	2392	(100)
5	A.5	1380	(57.7)	906	(37.9)	106	(4.4)	2392	(100)
6	A.6	1064	(44.5)	1129	(47.2)	199	(8.3)	2392	(100)
7	A.7	371	(15.5)	1670	(69.8)	351	(14.7)	2392	(100)
8	A.8	373	(15.6)	1820	(76.1)	199	(8.3)	2392	(100)
9	A.9	1101	(46.0)	1108	(46.3)	183	(7.7)	2392	(100)
10	A.10	710	(29.7)	1521	(63.6)	161	(6.7)	2392	(100)
11	A.11	380	(15.9)	1820	(76.1)	192	(8.0)	2392	(100)
12	A.12	468	(19.6)	1550	(64.8)	374	(15.6)	2392	(100)
13	A.13	1101	(46.0)	1033	(43.2)	258	(10.8)	2392	(100)
14	A.14	770	(32.2)	1423	(59.5)	199	(8.3)	2392	(100)
15	A.15	1003	(41.9)	1160	(48.5)	229	(9.6)	2392	(100)
16	A.16	1293	(54.1)	876	(36.6)	223	(9.3)	2392	(100)
17	A.17	1033	(43.2)	1145	(47.9)	214	(8.9)	2392	(100)
18	A.18	782	(32.7)	1366	(57.1)	244	(10.2)	2392	(100)
19	A.19	477	(19.9)	1590	(66.5)	325	(13.6)	2392	(100)
20	A.20	650	(27.2)	1544	(64.5)	198	(8.3)	2392	(100)
21	A.21	611	(25.5)	1388	(58.0)	393	(16.4)	2392	(100)
22	A.22	802	(33.5)	1217	(50.9)	373	(15.6)	2392	(100)
23	A.23	739	(30.9)	1388	(58.0)	265	(11.1)	2392	(100)

Table 5

Prevalence of students with Learning Difficulties (LDs) in Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills (AOMS) i.e., Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication & Division

Mathematical skills (Category)	Total Number of students assessed	Number of students with learning difficulties (LDs)	Prevalence of students with LDs
Arithmetic Operations (+, -, ×, ÷)	2392	272	$\frac{272}{2392} \times 100\% = 11.4\%$

Table 5 illustrates that the rate of prevalence of students with Learning difficulties in Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills (Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication & Division, i.e., +, -, ×, ÷) is 11.4% of the screen out, students.

Table 6

Prevalence of female students with Learning Difficulties (LDs) in Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills (AOMS) i.e., Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication & Division

Mathematical skills (Category)	Total Number of students assessed	Number of students with learning difficulties (LDs)	Prevalence of students with LDs
Arithmetic Operations (+, -, ×, ÷)	2392	192	$\frac{192}{2392} \times 100\% = 16.5\%$

Table 6 demonstrates that the prevalence of female students with Learning Difficulties in Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills (Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication & Division, i.e., +, -, ×, ÷) is 16.5% of the screen out, students.

Table 7

Prevalence of male students with Learning Difficulties (LDs) in Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills (AOMS) i.e., Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication & Division

Mathematical skills (Category)	Number of students assessed	Number of students with learning difficulties	Prevalence of students with LDs
Arithmetic Operations (+, -, ×, ÷)	2392	129	$\frac{129}{2392} \times 100\% = 10.5\%$

Table 7 validates that the prevalence of male students with Learning difficulties in Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills (Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication & Division, i.e., +, -, ×, ÷) is 10.5% of the screen out, students.

Table 8

Independent Sample t-test: Comparison of Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills of students with learning difficulties on the basis of gender

Description	N	M	df	t	Sig
Male	1150	15.04	1453	1.818	0.039
Female	1242	14.31	1209		

*P < .05 Significance Level

Table 8 confirms that the mean score of male students was 15.04 (stddev =.91), whereas the mean score of the female students was 14.31 (stddev =1.51). Furthermore, a student's independent sample t-test verified that this score .73 difference is significant ($t(2392) = 1.81, P < .05 = .039$), suggesting that a genuine difference in the Arithmetic Operation Mathematical Skills (AOMS) of the male and female students with learning difficulties.

Table 9

Independent Sample t-test: Comparison of Arithmetic Operations Mathematical Skills of students with learning difficulties on the basis of living area

Description	N	M	df	t	Sig
Rural	1230	16.40	1847	-1.479	.008
Urban	1162	18.17	1847		

*P < .05 Significance Level

Table 9 explains that the mean score of the students belongs to the rural areas was 16.40 (stddev =1.23), whereas the mean score of the students who belong to the urban living areas was 18.17 (stddev =.87). A student's independent sample t-test proved that this score 1.77 difference is significant ($t(2392) = -1.479, P <$

.05=.008), portentous that a real difference in the Arithmetic Operation Mathematical Skills (AOMS) of the rural and urban students with learning difficulties.

Findings & Conclusion

All discriminatory analyses revealed sufficient discrimination of the Arithmetic Operations Diagnostic Test (AODT). Cronbach's Alpha was .82 for the student's diagnostic test for the Arithmetic Operations Diagnostic Test (AODT). To establish the internal consistency of the test items, the test had an acceptable range of coefficient alpha. The arithmetic operations mathematical skills testing diagnosis diagnostic test is .60. This is the acceptable correlation between the diagnostic test and the pupils' success in elementary mathematics. The prevalence in number arithmetic procedures for children with learning problems was 11.4%, and the prevalence of male and female students with learning difficulties 10.5% and 16.5%, respectively.

The degree of accomplishment between low- and high-level students in mathematics was statistically significantly different in the arithmetic operation diagnostic test. However, the learning challenges in mathematics in arithmetical operations were not significantly different (addition, subtraction, multiplication, & division). It reveals that there are no differences in living conditions for pupils from urban and rural origins. However, the children living in urban regions have substantial difficulty in learning compared to the children who live in rural regions with a greater degree of learning challenges in mathematics and the challenges experienced in mathematics.

Prevalence of students with learning difficulties specifically in the field of mathematics, i.e., number count, the recognition of roman numerals, prime numbers, even numbers, odd numbers, understanding with numerical diffractions, the formation of large and small numbers, and the complementarity of almost tens and centuries was 16%. In the arithmetic operation of numbers, i.e., addition, subtraction, multiplication, & division, the prevalence rates of students with learning challenges were 11.4%. Difficulties in geometry-related topics were 14.9 percent for children with learning problems. In primary education, the overall frequency of kids with learning challenges was 15.5 percent.

Discussion & Recommendations

The data analysis for the research study revealed that several grey areas had been developed, including arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division), basic geometrical shapes, angle identification, types of angles, mathematical geometry, where students were confronted with learning difficulties. The diverse investigations have also backed this view. The psychologist for education Ormrod (2000) noted that most children in the school curriculum are likely to have more uncertainty and dissatisfaction with mathematics. Particularly because of the sequential and hierarchic conceptual character of mathematical education, the student who cannot mature early concepts and skills will find it more difficult to find new and more demanding materials in mathematics. Students with learning difficulties in mathematics tend to give up all confidence in comprehending the arithmetic and tend to memorize worthless information, procedures, symbols, and procedures repeatedly. Not unexpectedly, these pupils also have an extraordinarily bad viewpoint on the subject of math, improving the problem-scenario of their learning in the field of mathematics (Bhardwaj, 1987).

Math is a hierarchical and sequential field in which many concepts and competencies are interconnected, and early conceptions and competencies form the basis of later learning. It may be due to improper curricula that are incompatible with students' phases of development that students have learning problems in mathematics. It must be enhanced by the phases of growth provided by psychologists and curriculum specialists.

Poor teaching and education might be among the causes for students' learning difficulties in elementary school mathematics. The key part of the instruction is the teacher's content, which is relatively inadequate in most elementary schools. In particular, female elementary instructors have relatively little information on the curriculum of mathematics (Shashikala Devi, 1987).

The teacher's pedagogical abilities, which play a key role in student learning, might be very questionable in terms of the level of competence. For example, teachers do not use visual aids and specific materials to help them build concepts and skills (Mishra, 1998).

Interactive teaching may be lacking in the class with strong student participation. Teachers have insufficient in-service training for the skills of development students and link information with students' actual lives. It is because of this shortcoming that links may not be made between mathematics and real-life difficulties.

It's also a crucial truth that 58,000 teachers of elementary schools teach mathematics at various grades and topics. These teachers deal with Matric/PTC qualifications (DSD, Reports March 2016). They frequently do not upgrade their qualifications, which are required for the present modern age: new curricula, pedagogy, new methodologies, and requirements for the elementary education of the topic of mathematics. In short, poor education might be the explanation for learning difficulties at the primary level in the field of mathematics.

Teachers who teach mathematics in the 5th grade in primary education do not have adequate education in mathematics. The lack of continuing growth may be one of the causes of students' learning problems at the primary level in mathematics (Steele, 2006). In comparison with the other abilities like numbers, numerology in number, and geometry associated ideas, which are due to the red learning of students, the prevalence of students in pre-number conception is larger (Kothari, 1985).

In mathematics, the prevalence of females and males is 20.2% and 15.4%, respectively. The cause might be the detrimental attitude of female students towards mathematics backed by several studies of study. On the other hand, research also supports that boys are superior at mathematics to girls (<http://gender.stanford.edu/news/>). In addition, the girl is less rational than the boy (www.quora.com).

Students in rural and urban living regions have a considerable gap in their performance. Pei-A Liao, Hung-Hao Chang, Jiun-Hhao Wang, and Tai-Hsiung Horng (2013) have said that in comparison with urban pupils, rural pupils have always been worse. The explanation might be environmental elements, the absence of facilities, educational environment, people's contact, qualification to teachers, fewer interactions with advanced communities, etc. Jeff, David McCracken. David T. Barcinas (1991) observed that urban and rural students have a big change in their accomplishments, whereas rural students perform less than urban students. This may be attributed to the low-income group, differences in the connection between the community, school features, academic and professional quality of teachers, the number of facilities, etc.

It is recommended that further research in elementary, secondary, and secondary classrooms is advised at a macro level following this study. To find out the learning problems in various areas of mathematics, school instructors must utilize the designated diagnostic tool. Moreover, an advanced study should uncover challenges for such students in normal schools with comparison outlines for other language contents, including Urdu and English. Since girls have greater mathematics problems and difficulties, the instructor should guarantee that they are engaged with a particular focus. Furthermore, rural schools should include children in physical and graphical mathematical challenges such as diagrams and hands-on materials to include mathematical principles.

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